

Doctoral Program Learning Module on Developing Leading Practice in Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students: Cased Study Learning Activities Independentstudies In Thailand

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 23, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Doctoral Program Development, Leading Teacher Development, Critical Comparative Analysis, Creative Thinking for Enhancement, Action Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5129181</p>	<p><i>The purposes of this study were to: 1) create and develop effective doctoral learning module on leading student's development program to enhance critical thinking for thesis writing and 2) evaluate the developed module on its efficiency and effectiveness- its congruence of utility, possibility, and appropriateness, learning achievement of learners, learning retention, and the learners' satisfaction. Samples were 4 Doctoral degree students in Educational Administration and Development and Leadership program, Northeastern University, Khon Kaen Province, Thailand. Statistics used were percentage, mean, standard deviation, effectiveness index, and t-test. The results were: 1) The developed module on learning activity management of leading teachers in simulation situation had 16 Modules: (1.1) Survey of former experience (1.2) Collaboration in planning (1.3) The development of creative students' conception (1.4) The application of thinking approach (1.5) Practice in classroom (1.6) Supervision, follow up, and evaluation (1.7) Feedback and reinforcement (1.8) Seminar for enhancing strength, publication cased studies and (1.9) Reflection learning. 2) The efficiency and effectiveness of the developed module were: (2.1) The efficiency of 85.46 (E1) /82.59 (E2) which were higher than the committed 80/80 standard, (2.2) The congruence of utility, possibility, and appropriateness were in the highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.69$, $SD = 0.42$), (2.3) The effectiveness index was 0.7465 which meant students gained more knowledge of 74.65%, (2.4) The students had significantly higher learning achievement after learning via the module at the level of 0.01, (2.5) There was no significant differences of learning achievement between after learning and after learning for two weeks which mean the students' learning retention, and (2.6) The students had satisfaction on the developed module in the highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.65$, $SD = 0.41$), and all pass skill program of learners module in the excellence ($\bar{x} = 2.53$, $SD = 0.21$).</i></p>

Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Knowledge could be changed as the dynamic. In the 21st century, learners should be adapted their learning from gaining knowledge to some necessary skills of cooperation and creating creative innovation. Consequently, learners should have chances to gain knowledge from various sources outside classroom to practice analyzing, criticizing, deciding, solving problems, and creating new knowledge which occurring the integration outside classroom activities and inside classroom. Panich (2013) stated that teachers should not teach but advise their learners to have creative thinking, working together, creating and developing efficiency works. Teachers were the fundamental of changing especially those, who have prepared innovative learning conditions to create learning inspiration of learners via practice, have changed the teachers' role from teachers to tutors or coaches that could create learninginspirations.

In Thailand, Office of the Education Council, Ministry of Education, Thailand (2010) had done the research about the policy of developing teachers and educational personnel, the result showed the condition of learning management that though learners had been trained, they had some problems on low learning achievement and lacking of desirable characteristics on critical thinking and solving problems skills. Developing the innovation program for critical thinking enhancement to the secondary school leading teachers was a part of the subject Contrastive Study of Critical Comparative Analysis of Thai Education Management Global and Regional Society (ED41201)in semester 1, 2020 of doctoral students in Educational Administration and Leadership, and improved for Doctoral Program Learning Module on Developing Leading Students in Educational policy and

strategic Plan Development in Thailand(ED41306) in semester 2,2020 of doctoral students.We choose the part to be our content and had done our educational research and development on creating and developing an integrative learning module on the purpose to be used via Google classroom, which was an innovative learning conditions of learners via flipped classroom techniques.

1.2 Background

Jonathan and Aaron's flipped classroom was the new techniques of learning management focus on teaching less learning more (Bergmann, & Sams, 2012). Flipped classroom comprised online learning, online media, information technology, various communication, and doing activities in classroom. It could support learners' self-practices in class, by using information technology and various communication, focusing on creating self-knowledge and individualized competency through self-paced. Moreover, they could have interaction with their peers and teachers in flipped classroom. According to Panich (2013) and Weangsamoot (2009), it had to use various techniques which would be useful and necessity in developing teachers to have skills in learning management. Since enhancing skills of learning management creatively, understanding differences individually would be recognized because it caused the skills of designing learning management individually.We choose a learning module which has been an educational innovation technique used in flipped classroom. It was the inspiration in learning management that supported learners to have analytical thinking. By using the module that was well systematically prepared, learners got their learning achievements. They have had their post-test scores significantly 0.1-0.5 higher than their pre- test one (Suda, 2005; Donbundit, 2008; Inruangsri, 2011; Paphaphasid, 2018. Moreover, the create learning activities management world of occur efficiently and effectively by doing in real context, and direct experience and students group knowledge. Chantarasombat, Udombunyanupab, & Kenchaiyawong, 2018), and their satisfaction was in the highest level (Hasakool, Chianchana, & Stirayakorn, 2016;Krongtanoen,2016; Chantarasombat, Udombunyanupab, & Kenchaiyawong, 2018,Chantarasombat, & Meekhamtong, 2020), Chantarasombat& Sirisuthi, 2020), Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021), Sirisuthi &Chantarasombat, 2021),In semester 1, 2020, we had started the learning module for doctoral students in Educational Administration and Leadership at Northeastern University, Khon Kaen, Thailand, by studying elements and factors including the current and desirable condition of Thai learning management in enhancing the critical thinking of the secondary school teachers before creating the program by using google classroom technique. We used 5 experts and 2 pre-test groups who were not our research population to evaluate our module. Their feedbacks had been used to develop the module for improving learning and teaching focusing on participating between teachers, administrators, and academic persons before offering the module to the doctoral students.

3. Research Questions

3.1 How could the learning module of leader-teacher in learning management for enhancing Developing Leading Practice in Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Independent studies on Educational Administration and Leadershipcritical thinking of the high school students, in the Subject of Contrastive Study of Developing Leading Practice in Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Cased studies on Educational Administration and Leadership (ED41207), be created and developed?

3.2 How much did its achievements be evaluated on: it's appropriate, possible, related, and useful by experts, on the students effectively at 80/80, on index of its effectiveness, on the learning achievement, on the learning retention, and on students' satisfaction of the module?

4. Research Objectives are as follows:

1.4.1 To study the factors of learning management in enhancing the critical thinking of the high school students

1.4.2 To investigate the current and desirable condition of learning management in enhancing critical thinking of the high school students

1.4.3 To create the program of leader-student in learning management for enhancing critical thinking of high school students by using google classroom technique

1.4.4 To develop the program of leader-student in learning management for enhancing critical thinking of the high school students in the Subject of Developing Leading Practice in Learning Activities Independent studies on Educational Administration and Leadership(ED41207) for students by using google classroom technique

1.4.5 To evaluate the quality of the program of leader-teacher in learning management for enhancing critical thinking of the secondary school teachers in the Subject of Contrastive Study of Developing Leading Practice in Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Independent studies on Educational Administration and Leadership(ED41207) for students by using google classroom technique

1.4.6 To compare pre and posttest scores of the learning achievement of the students who use the program of leader-student in learning management for enhancing critical thinking of the high school in Subject of Learning Independent studies on Educational Administration and Leadership(ED41207)students by using google classroom technique.

5 Research Conceptual Framework

The development of the learning module and the conceptual framework was determined by the authors with experts' evaluations. The innovation of the learning module consisted of 9 learning sub-modules including 1: surveying the former experience, 2: planning, 3: creating comprehension, 4: applying the idea, 5: practicing in class, 6: supervision and assessing, 7: giving feedback and giving support, 8: seminar, and 9: giving reflection. As shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the study of developing the program of leader Students' in learning management for enhancing critical thinking

2. Research Methodology

1. Construction and Development of Research Instruments

Steps of setting and/or developing the research instruments could be divided into 3 parts: 1) To create and develop the learning module, 2) To create and develop the learning achievement tests, and 3) To create and develop the satisfaction questionnaires

2.1 To create and develop the learning module as follow;

2.1.1.1 Brainstorming and planning for developing a learning module for doctoral students in Educational

Administration and Leadership, Northeastern University, Khon Kaen, Thailand.

2.1.1.2 Investigating concepts, theories, principles, policies, and strategies of educational administration

on learning in 21st century. Moreover, researchers analyzed the basic information, the condition, problems of learning management, and developing teachers to identify issues of developing. Furthermore, the researchers investigated the scope of the study, theories, and related review in learning management for enhancing critical thinking of the secondary school teachers by criticizing factors occurring. The questionnaires were used to enhance the secondary teachers which could support them to get the rewards for the innovation of learning management in the northeastern of Thailand. The data from 4 peoples who answering the questionnaire with 9

modules and factors were examined by 5 experts again. After that, all factors were combined and defined to find the detail to form the program and documents presented 5 experts later.

2.1.1.3 Finding the relation of the content and learning module. Researchers defined vision of the module and created its planning structures to achieve the objectives of the program and to enhance the people in the experiment, had vision, and had critical thinking in steps of learning management. There were studying, designing, developing and using the module. The module instrument included facilities, and a guide book. The guide book could help users understand easily and it was examined by the experts. Beside these, there were assessing and examining. The fundamental concepts to define the schedule of the module included concepts, participatory learning, advising, practicing, supervision, suggestion, giving feedback, and the theories related to the nature of teachers. The result form the experts showed that the planning module was appropriate, possible, related, and useful in the highest level.

2.1.1.4 Offering 9 units of the learning program to the groups who were not the research population; 1) group of 5 people, then improved in the illustrations and recorded, and 2) group of 9 people, including the doctoral degree students in Education Administration 1 in semester 2, 2019. The result showed that the effectiveness was at 82.50/80.36 which similar to the setting standard.

2.2 To create and develop learning achievement test as follow;

2.2.1 Investigating theories, principles, and concepts to create the achievement test on the theory of Sri sa-ard (2010).

2.2.2 Multiple choices were used to create the achievement test with 4 choices, including 40 questions and the test comprised only 30 questions.

2.2.3 After preparing the test, it was presented to the experts to evaluate and find relation between the behavioral objectives. The criteria of grading the test were 1) +1 when the test was assessed by the behavioral objectives, 2) 0 when the test was not clear from behavioral objectives, and 3) -1 when the test was not assessed by the behavioral objectives.

2.2.4 Analyzing the data to find the index of effectiveness between the questions of the test and the behavioral objectives using IOC (Pattiyatane, 2008). If the IOC of the test was at 0.5-1.00, the test was reliability.

2.2.5 After finding IOC, the test were used with 23 master degree students, the major of Education Administration, in the subject of Seminar for Educational Administration in order to observe the students' behavior during doing the test, how did they spend their time doing the test, how did they understand the test, and how did they answer the questions.

2.2.6 After finishing the test, the scores of the test were calculated to find the difficulty (P) and discrimination of each question. After calculating, the result showed that P of the test was at 0.40-0.80 and the discrimination of the test was at 0.20-0.60. After finding the reliability of the test, it was at 0.84. Then the test could use with the research.

2.3 To create and develop satisfaction questionnaires, comprised of 9 parts with 45 questions as follow;

2.3.1 Investigating theories, principles, and concepts on the satisfaction of Suntrayuth (2008).

2.3.2 Studying techniques of doing the questionnaire (Sri sa-ard, 2010).

2.3.3 Educating and creating questionnaires of satisfaction based on the objectives using 5 rating scales.

2.3.4 Presenting the questionnaire to the experts to assess the relation between the questions and the objectives. The criteria were the same as the achievement test.

2.3.5 Analyzing the data to find the index of effectiveness between the questions of the questionnaire and the behavioral objectives using IOC (Pattiyatane, 2008). The IOC of the questionnaire was at 0.80-1.00. The experts suggested that language usage should arrange by following the grammar correction, the sentences should be clear, and if there were some sentences that are similar in meaning, those sentences should be concluded and made only one sentence.

2.3.6 Using the questionnaire with the groups who were not the research population, including 30 master degree students of Education Administration, and the group of teachers and supervisors in Khon Kaen Primary Education Service Area Office. The results would be analyzed to find discrimination (r_{xy}) on each question during 0.32-0.81 and the questionnaires would be analyzed to find the reliability with the α - Coefficient using Cronbach alpha technique (Sri sa-ard, 2010). The reliability was 0.94.

2.4 *Data Collection and Analysis*

2.4.1 The efficiency and effectiveness of the learning module was analyzed by using the Mean and Percentage of Brahmawong (2013). The efficiency was searched for by using E_1/E_2 Formula as follows:

$$E_1 = \frac{\sum X/N}{A} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{\sum F/N}{B} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The effectiveness index of the learning module was analyzed by using the following E.I. formula.

$$\text{Effectiveness Index (E.I.)} = \frac{\text{The sum of the post-test score} - \text{The sum of pre-test score}}{(\text{Student Number X Full Score}) - \text{The sum of the pre-test score.}} \quad (3)$$

2.4.2 The student's knowledge and learning retention data was collected by pre-test and post-test learning scores from the learning achievement test while the learning retention had to be collected after the post-test which was performed 2 weeks later. Comparison of the learning achievement of the learning module was analyzed by mean values of t-test (Dependent) comparative analysis between pre-score and post-score (Sri sa-ard, 2010).

2.4.3 The satisfaction on the learning module data was collected by using the satisfaction questionnaire. It was analyzed by using the Mean value (\bar{X}) and Standard Deviation ($S.D.$) for measuring the satisfaction level.

3. Results

3.1 The factors of critical thinking of the secondary school teachers comprised of 10 factors ; 1) teachers prepared various learning activities, 2) teachers presented motivated activities, 3) teachers offered learning activities in different places, 4) teachers offered learning activities emphasizing on child center, 5) teachers used technology in learning management, 6) teachers offered activities related to daily life, 7) teachers used innovation in learning activities, 8) the activities were cooperated with the community, 9) the activities were emphasized on teaching moral, and 10) the activities were assessed and evaluated. The study found that current condition of learning management for enhancing critical thinking of the secondary school students were at moderate level. When considering on each factor, the experts agreed with the teachers about preparing various learning activities and using technology in learning management. The desirable condition was at the highest level, too. As shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Creative Module of Leadership Program for Learning Management in Enhancing the Critical Thinking of the high school students: Learning Activities Independent studies on Educational Administration and Leadership(ED41207) students

The program in learning management for enhancing critical thinking of the secondary school students Including: 1) the principal of the program, 2) the objectives of the program, 3) the goal of the program, 4) the content of the program development. The content included into 9 modules: 1) the survey of experiences, 2) the planning, 3) the concepts, 4) the applied concepts, 5) the classroom implementation, 6) the supervision, monitoring and evaluating of the study, 7) the feedback and reinforcement, 8) the seminar for strengthening, and 9) the presentation at the academic conference. The final parts of the module focused on doing activities outside

classroom. The researchers defined activities on learning by doing under advising and helping continuously. The learners who participated must have plans, and review the principals from the beginning to face with real practicing. It meant that there were advisors who gave advices, taught, and gave feedback continuously. This process could make the understanding. The treatment included training, and self-development which including 6 steps; 1) preparation, 2) training, 3) understanding thoroughly, 4) verifying and evaluating, 5) strengthening, and 6) giving feedback. The results from the experts' evaluation showed that the benefits, possibilities, correcting, and suitability at the highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.69$, $SD=0.42$).

3.2 The results from the research about the module found its achievement as follows;

3.2.1 The program had the efficiency of the process for the learning outcome (E1 / E2) at 85.46/ 82.59 which higher than the criteria at 80/80.

3.2.2 The effectiveness index for the program was at 0.7465 which explaining that students gain higher knowledge 74.65%.

3.2.3 The students who were taught by the module gained their learning post-test score higher than their pre-test scores significantly at .05. After teaching, their learning retention data shown the students gained similar scores from the posttest and after 2 weeks of teaching. It was clear that students' learning retention scores by the module was stable.

3.2.4 The students' satisfaction from the module was at the highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.52$, $SD=0.41$).

4. Discussions

4.1 The evaluation results from the experts showed the success of the learning module at high level ($\bar{X} = 4.69$) and when finding the effectiveness of the program found that the program was efficiency at 85.46/82.59. It was because the module was well developed systematically through theories, researching, and examining by experts which supported its efficiency related to Suda (2005); Donbudit (2008); Inruangsri (2011); Paphaphasid (2018) and Chantarasombat, Udombunyanupab, & Kenchaiyawong (2018); Chantarasombat & Rooyuenyong (2020) Chantarasombat, & Meekhamtong (2020), Chantarasombat & Sirisuthi (2020), Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021), Sirisuthi & Chantarasombat, (2021), that with the module that was well systematically prepared, learners could get their learning achievements from its effectiveness.

4.2 The program could enhance understanding, attitude, and skills of learning management. The comparison of learning management before and after using the program found that learners had the 'skills of learning management higher than before using the module significantly at .01. Students who studied by the program were effectively at 85.46 / the effectiveness of the result was 82.59 higher than 80/80. The index of effectiveness was higher 74.65 % and had retention in learning after studying 2 weeks. It was because the module had been improved several steps in the process of research and development, then was standardized by experts. The module was designed to have relearning for students starting from theories to practices. Beside this, the module focused on doing activities outside classroom, on learning by doing under advising and helping continuously. It meant that there were advisors who gave advices, taught, and gave feedback continuously. This process could make the understanding, the knowledge was retention and comprehended deeply in learning management.

4.3 The follow factors contributed the high score, overall high score and excellence skill program of learners were: 4.3.1 The authors thoroughly studied the curriculum, related documents, and research literature in constructing the learning module, which they revised, corrected, and improved by the experts' recommendations. The research findings highlighted that the overall quality of the developed learning module, after the experts' evaluation, was at "The Highest" level. The quality of propriety, feasibility, congruency, and aspects, was also at the "The Highest" level.

4.3.2 The authors tested the developed learning model with the sampling groups they had selected and also the group that had volunteered. The trial results showed that efficiency was 82.67/83.89. During the trial test, the authors personally collected the data from the participants and were present during the tests. The students' participation in the activities and observations were not perfect, but they were continuously improved upon to find the strengths and weaknesses during the trial period. The team of experts indicated that the content of the learning module included a variety of diverse activities that can create innovative knowledge and ignite creativity. The experts also noted that the learning module can be applied to other educational programs and curriculums. The experts also pointed out the weakness in the construction, namely that the efficiency of the trial test would be muted or not as efficient because the participants lacked a handbook or reference guide of the learning module. As a result, the researchers created, published and made available a handbook to all participants before the test trials began, thus making the learning module complete. Trial tests with the sampling group were satisfactory and

the authors carefully checked the learning module until they were confident that it was perfect and could meet the target's criterion.

The high efficiency index of the developed learning model is consistent with Inruengsri's (2011) findings. The research findings indicated that the learning module, including the rationale, reason, objective, basic knowledge, basic evaluation, learning activity, post-test evaluation, and remedial teaching, had an efficiency of 83.88/85.96. by Donpraipan (2013) achieved similar scores. The efficiency of the learning module in Sufficiency Economy Philosophy was 79.66/82.77 with a specified criterion 80/80. Krongdanern (2016) found that the learning module Sequence had an efficiency of 83.30/84.55, which was higher than the specified criterion. Hasakun (2016) established the training module for instructional management as a part of a handbook of a short-term training program management in IOP model application, and found that the suitability of programs was in "The Highest" level and "High" level. The congruency was in the "High" level in every aspect. The theoretical achievement was 81.60/80.49%. The achievement was 79.42%. The theoretical achievement was 82.32/81.41%. In practice, the achievement was 79.91%, which was higher than the criterion in both the theoretical and practical aspect. Papapasit (2018) found that the efficiency of the self-study Classroom Research was higher than the standard criterion 80 / 80, at 81.53/88.46. Rowland (1995) found that the developed learning module, was efficient, and that the students obtained supplementary knowledge and discipline.

The authors applied the correct theoretical approach and practices, which resulted in a learning model that was appropriate for teachers to utilize for students' development. Indeed, the learning module is an effective educational innovation that can assist students in achieving their full potential. Chantarasombat (2020) found out that the efficiency of the self-study Classroom Research was higher than the standard criterion 80 / 80, at 84.67/83.00. Besides, Chantarasombat observed the effectiveness index management of students learning module for students was 0.6577, indicating that the students had an increased knowledge for 65.77 %.

The students' post-test learning achievement scores were significantly higher than the pre-test at .05 level, because the learning activity was an action learning process, as the activities focused on authenticity, real-world situations, and student-centered learning. It was necessary to provide the students with as many tangible practices as possible, so that they would have direct experience and properly exercise their skills. Practices and activities should be based on their satisfaction and divided into individual activities, group activities, and activities for the entire class. Student-centered learning activities provide students with more skill practices and are an important factor that increases the speed of self-learning in acquiring new knowledge and development of critical thinking processes. Chantarasombat(2018),Chantarasombat &Sirisuthi (2020), Chantarasombat & Meekhamtong's (2020), Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit's (2021), Sirisuthi &Chantarasombat (2021). This view is supported by Dechakupt's (2011) assertion that the student-centered instructional management guidelines focused on the development of new knowledge and also innovative thinking through intellectual processes and teamwork. The students must interact and participate as well as learn how to become a teacher, and eventually be capable of applying the gained knowledge. Experts investigated the applied learning module and found that the efficiency was also at "The Highest" level. Students viewed that the activities were stimulating and the language of the questions was easy to understand, which enabled them to answer more accurately. No significant differences occurred in post-test learning achievement scores and post-test learning achievement scores after two weeks, suggesting that the learning module had allowed to achieve learning retention.

The learning module motivated students because of their direct participation in the activities, as they gained new knowledge from elements and surroundings with which they were familiar. Awareness and relatable environments produce good conduct through simple techniques without excessively complicated activities. Each learning sub-module included activities in analytical thinking techniques and synthesis. Selecting simple, recognizable stimulates enthusiasm. When selecting an appropriate learning activity, a teacher has to ensure basic knowledge in the learning management principle and determine the learning objective in order to guide the students. Familiarity stimulates learning interests, entices better cooperation, and improves learning competency; also, the students can apply it in their daily life.

Consideration of the participants' differences and creating an enjoyable learning atmosphere simplified the learning activities and provided a welcoming instructional ambiance. Creating a pleasant learning atmosphere throughout the learning activities is consistent with Kaemmanee's (2013) findings that the effectiveness index of students' learning management through the learning module Educational Policy, Strategy, and Strategic Plan (EDA6201) was 0.6577 or 65.77% with Chantarasombat (2020), findings that the effectiveness index of students' learning management through the learning module Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities (ED41201) was 0.7397 or 73.97 % with Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021). This author showed that 65.77%, and 73.97% of the students could learn more and were content. A pleasant learning experience is the ideal instructional setting; thus, teachers and instructors should seek out various learning techniques and adopt them in the student's development. The important factors to contemplate

include: The lessons must be useful and meaningful, the learning activities should be diverse, the learning media should be interesting, evaluation should be emphasized on each student's potential, and the interaction between the teachers and students should be friendly, compassionate, encouraging, and supportive of each other.

Knowledge, skill practice, and students' attitude should be key when conducting evaluations. Behavioral observation, performance scrutiny, examination, and evaluating findings should be performed and informed regularly to improve the efficiency of the activity. The learning media should be based on an informal instructional process with minimum complexity. Systematically utilizing the developed learning module yielded efficient learning achievements and a high effectiveness index. Samersak's (2005) research supported the same level of success based on the high vocational certificate program 2003 in the Electrical Power Course. The results concluded that the experimental group's learning achievement scores were significantly higher than those of the control group students at .01 level. Donbundit (2008) found that the overall post-test score was significantly higher than the pretest at .01. Krongtanern (2016) found that the post-test scores in learning achievement of students in the mathematics learning module Sequence were significantly higher than those in the pre-test at .01 level. Nelson (1994), who constructed the learning module for enhancing and encouraging patients being treated by nitroglycerin, found that their knowledge and morale were increased more than those of patients who only studied through documents at .001 level.

The students' overall satisfaction was in "The Highest" level, because the developed learning module was innovative and interesting, and had diverse learning activities that coincided with the students' competency. The learning activities challenged the students' interests. This is consistent with Koonchon Na Ayutthaya's (1993), Chantarasombat & Sirisuthi 2020, Chantarasombat & Meekhamtong 2020, Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021), Sirisuthi & Chantarasombat (2021). theoretical approach and principle in the construction of learning modules. This author recommended the following:

1. Learning module constructors should regularly consider the general objective of the program and carefully examine whether the objective of the lesson can develop students' competency as specified. The instructional activity management should be congruent with the instructional philosophy of the program.
2. Teachers should define the competency to be learned by students.
3. The designers should determine the level of basic competency for the students and should only be centered on the basic issue of the lesson. If possible, they should set the basic competency at the minimum level for flexibility.
4. Basic evaluations should always be refined, so that the criterion could accurately measure the students' competency relating to the objective. The evaluation should be grounded in reality and provide feedback for students. The most efficient measurement technique should be taken into consideration and designers should participate in the diagnosis of the weak points.
5. The designers should provide various alternatives to students, so that they could select what would be most helpful for them to succeed and be congruent with their learning styles. The learning experience should also help them to learn in a short period. The students should have an opportunity to select and construct their activities with their teachers' support.
6. The teacher should prioritize the learning activities and inform the students, so that they are aware and understand each stage of the activities before commencement.
7. The students' selected activities should provide equal opportunity for all participants to practice.
8. The pre-test should be reliable and must accurately measure the student's achievements. Pre-test evaluations should follow the same guidelines for the basic evaluation.
9. The designers should specify corrective learning activities appropriately. These activities should be dependent and specific, and must be applied after pretest evaluations. Corrective learning activities can also be included as a selective choice for students to participate.
10. The description of the learning module should be precisely defined.
11. The designers should allow as many co-workers and students as possible, to comment on the learning module, so the constructed lessons and activities can be corrected and improved.
12. The designers should always revise to see whether the completed lesson focused on the competency of student development and if the lesson is a good example of efficient education.
13. Learning modules and activities must always be flexible and allowed to be modified and adapted to meet students' requirements and satisfaction. Charoenpong (2012), Chantarasombat & Rooyuenyong (2020), Chantarasombat & Meekhamtong 2020, Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021), Sirisuthi & Chantarasombat (2021) successfully applied many of the suggestions of the advocated learning module. This author found that the students' satisfaction was in "The Highest" level.

5. Recommendations

5.1 Recommendations for Application and Development

5.1.1 The administrators and those, who involved with the development of quality of education and students in high school education service area and in other educational institutes, should enhance the use of the designed program for creative thinking enhancements to support learning activity management in secondary schools. The module was a standard one because it systematically approved by the experts and experimented to be authentically implemented. Beside this, it was revised and edited several times to be an effective module for developing teachers to be knowledgeable and be skillful on managing learning activity with creativity.

5.1.2 For implementing the designed module, for learning management in enhancing the Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Cased studies on Educational Administration and Leadership in the high school students, most effectively according with the objectives of the program, it should use the module continuously in both theoretical part and practical part in which the teachers could practice their teaching in real situations. The process on the module would help the teachers to participate in training. They could be capable on implementing their knowledge and experience from their learning to the real practice systematically. Furthermore, the evaluations and follow-up sessions were also needed in order to be the teachers' suggestions and guidelines for teachers in every stage of the module so they could apply the obtained knowledge for their effectively and confidently teaching.

5.1.3 Process of learning activities in the module had focused on practicing to enhance learning management skills for teachers. On applying the module, it needed to emphasize on the teachers participating in the development program to follow every stage specified. The support from their school administrators, school supervisors and their teachers' colleagues could enhance the teachers' knowledge, understanding, and positive attitude as well as their leadership skill in learning management according to the objectives of the program.

5.1.4 The Office of the Education Commission should set the national policy to promote and support schools for developing teachers' skill for classroom management to enhance students' critical thinking. They should also promote model teachers' roles to be teachers who taught and learn with students, to be teachers who known and have do research works to achieve the goals effectively. Thai classroom management to enhance the secondary school students' critical thinking, both government and private schools, should be integrated with Google classroom and started from the schools with readiness.

5.2 Recommendations for future research

5.2.1 This educational research and development was conducted to study the Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Cased studies on Educational Administration and Leadership thinking in students' learning management. There should be a research on developing students' creative thinking in other aspects of their tasks, such as the development of students' critical thinking on classroom research, on doing project, on providing students' assistance, or on designing teaching materials, etc.

5.2.2 This study had emphasized on the development of creative thinking for teachers' skill of classroom management by using development module. There should be the study to enhance teachers' critical thinking through other learning techniques, such as training, school-based training, or workshop in order to compare those techniques for learning activity management which could appropriately provide knowledge of development.

5.2.3 The effectiveness of the module was examined by comparing the knowledge and understanding, skill and attitude of students in learning activity management toward creative learning management before and after using the module. The suggestion for the further research was to investigate whether the knowledge and understanding, skill and attitude of students were related to creative learning activities.

6. Conclusion

The learning module on developing the innovation program for critical thinking enhancement to the high school leading students was a part of the subject Contrastive Study of Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Cased studies on Educational Administration and Leadership (ED41207) students was created and developed as an educational research and development. With well-organized and revised, it responded the objectives of the doctoral program on creating knowledge on enhancing critical thinking with students' comprehension, good attitude and skills for managing learning activities creatively.

And the skills were a part of the subject Contrastive Study of Creative Thinking for Enhancement of Students' Learning Activities Cased studies on Educational Administration and Leadership for 3 students were 3 reports entitle: 1) Development of Digital Technology Leadership Development Program for School Administrators Under the Office of Primary Educational Service Area 2) The program of English instructors' competency for Learning in 21st century and 3) The Development of educational management model to Enhance education quality toward excellence of the Office of the Secondary Educational Service Area.

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development in order to develop learning package innovation to be an effective learning model in according with the needs of the users and stakeholders.

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